

Research Article

Vitamin A deficiency and Ocular manifestation among rural children aged 6-15 in Tajikistan

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Abstract:

Vitamin A deficiency is major concern especially for the children living in developing countries. According to UNICEF, around one-third of children do not receive adequate Vitamin A supplementation. The present study focuses on Vitamin A deficiency and Ocular manifestation among rural children aged 6-15 in Tajikistan. Anemia is a major public health concern among women of reproductive age (WRA) and is associated with high maternal and infant morbidity and mortality. This community-based cross-sectional study was done vitamin A deficiency survey of children aged 6-15 in Tajikistan (rural areas).

The study included a sample of children of mixed socio-economic status who reside in municipalities of high social vulnerability located in Tajikistan. The sample size studied in this survey was 276 children of aged 6-15 years, prevalence of vitamin A deficiency at 95% confidence level. In the current research, 169 (61.23) children had vitamin A deficiency, with anemia in 154 (55.79%) of them, iodine deficiency in 193 (9.92%), conjunctival xerosis in ocular manifestations, 0.36% of Bitot's spots, corneal xerosis in 1.08%, and keratomalacia missing.

Keywords: Vitamin A deficiency, Ocular manifestation, rural children, Tajikistan

Introduction

Vitamin A is an important vitamin needed in modest amounts, primarily for the visual system, growth and development, maintaining epithelial cellular integrity, immunological function, and reproduction. [1]. Inadequate vitamin A consumption is the major cause of vitamin A deficiency. Nowadays, VAD is one of the most serious issues among public health problems since many children and pregnant women are affected by Vitamin A deficiency condition in poor nations. [2, 3].

The RDA for vitamin A varies by age and gender. If vitamin A consumption falls below the recommended allowance, a number of symptoms may arise, commonly known as Vitamin A Deficiency Disorders (VAD).[6,7]

Vitamin A plays a major role in various biological phenomenon and it can't be produced naturally in human body, hence it must be consumed via diet resources.4 VAD among children is also associated with increased child mortality mainly due to detrimental effects on the immune system.[7] According to a report from UNICEF, vitamin A can increase child's chance of survival by 12–24 percent[8].

Malnutrition is a widespread health problem, particularly affecting the low- and middle-income countries. Adequate maternal nutrition during pregnancy and lactation is important for the promotion of optimal health during early development of the infant. Stunting, as a result of chronic malnutrition, can only be fully reversed if addressed efficiently within the first 2 years of life [9]. Iron deficiency (ID) and the consequential ID anaemia (IDA) in early life can lead to poor cognitive and motor development [10].

Paradoxically, many parts of the world are currently exposed to an overweight and obesity epidemic, with over 39% of adults being overweight worldwide, caused by an energy imbalance between consumption and expenditure [13]. As a consequence, noncommunicable diseases like cardiovascular

diseases, diabetes, musculoskeletal disorder, and some cancers are increasing [11,12,14].

Previous Tajik National Nutritional Surveys (TNNS) have been conducted in 2003 and 2009 (Ministry of Health Republic of Tajikistan and United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], [15,16]). In 2009, an association between overweight/obesity and anaemia in children under 5 years was investigated, but no association could be confirmed, and with this, no intraindividual double burden of malnutrition [17].

In response, the article by Mason et al., several researchers [18,19,20] directly disputed their proposed policy shift. In brief, researchers identified multiple design flaws of the DEVTA trial and cited repeated criticisms of the DEVTA trial's methods and conclusions [18], attributed near elimination of severe VAD, xerophthalmia, and childhood blindness to VAS [19], and stated that more studies are needed before any phase out of VAS can be conducted [20]. In line with the Global Alliance for Vitamin A (GAVA) recommendations [21], these researchers [18] also suggested that countries should only consider scaling back VAS programs in populations where there is evidence that VAD is no longer a public health problem (i.e., <5% prevalence of VAD).

Anemia is a major public health concern among women of reproductive age (WRA) and is associated with high maternal and infant morbidity and mortality [22,23]. Anemia occurs when the number and size of red blood cells or the hemoglobin (Hb) concentration fall below an established cut-off value, consequently impairing the capacity of the blood to transport oxygen to the body [24,22]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has dened anemia as Hb levels of <12.0 g/dL among WRA [25]. According to the WHO estimates, about half a billion WRA are anemic worldwide, of those around 20.2 million women are severely anemic with a

higher burden in low-middle-income countries [26].

On a global scale, UN agencies and non-governmental organizations should provide technical assistance for national micronutrient surveys. National program planners should make evidence-based decisions, and if biochemical data on VA status are insufficient, it should be gathered before program adjustments are implemented.

This study will assist prioritize groups for vitamin A supplementation and create targeted treatments to address malnutrition among children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This community-based cross-sectional study was done vitamin A deficiency survey of children aged 6-15 in Tajikistan (rural areas). The study included a sample of children of mixed socio-economic status who reside in municipalities of high social vulnerability located in Tajikistan. The sample size studied in this survey was 276 children of aged 6-15 years, prevalence of vitamin A deficiency at 95% confidence level.

Data were collected using a pretested semi-structured questionnaire were updated to provide the most relevant information on the health and nutritional status for children under 15 years. Four villages from selected districts were chosen to create a sampling frame. Thirty five households were selected from each village, and kids aged 6 to 15 was chosen from each. The questionnaire asked about the participant's age, gender, residence, education, employment, income of parents, Education of parents. Qualified physicians checked all children in daylight for vitamin A deficiency. Ocular manifestation was adopted in the study, Ocular manifestation was diagnosed if there was history of night blindness, or there were signs of conjunctival xerosis, Bitot's spots, corneal xerosis and keratomalacia on clinical examination.

Ethics: The study was approved by the Institutional ethical committee. Written informed consent was also obtained from the parents of children.

Statistical analysis

It was performed by statistical software SPSS version 20. Association between VAD and different socio-demographic variables was assessed by using chi-square test. The prevalence of ocular manifestations of VAD with 95% confidence intervals (CI) by state, age group and gender was analysed. P value of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

The current study comprised 276 children:

- The total number of children in the study was 276
- 24.27% of the children were in the 6-8 age group
- 39.49% of the children were in the 9-11 age group
- 36.23% of the children were in the 12-15 age group

As a gender variable, there were 175 male children (63.40%) and 101 female children (36.59%). The majority of parents had the occupation Labour 191 (69.20%), with the rest having Job/service 85 (30.79%), with a higher socioeconomic class of 71 (25.72), middle 129 (46.73), and lower 76 (27.53%). In terms of parents' education, 109 (39.49%) were illiterate, 151 (54.71%) had attended school, and 16 (5.79%) had finished higher education. In the current research, 169 (61.23) children had vitamin A deficiency, with anemia in 154 (55.79%) of them, iodine deficiency in 193 (9.92%), conjunctival xerosis in ocular manifestations, 0.36% of Bitot's spots, corneal xerosis in 1.08%, and keratomalacia missing.

Table1: Distribution of study participants according to their demographic profile and Ocular manifestation status (N=276)

Variables		Frequency (N=276)	Percentage %
Age group (in years)	6-8	67	24.27
	9-11	109	39.49
	12-15	100	36.23
Gender	Male	175	63.40
	Female	101	36.59
Occupation of parents	Labour	191	69.20
	Service/Business	85	30.79
Socio economic status of parents	Upper	71	25.72
	Middle	129	46.73
	Lower	76	27.53
Parents Education	illiterate	109	39.49
	Schooling	151	54.71
	Higher studies	16	5.79
Anemia	Present	154	55.79
	Absent	122	44.20
Vitamin A Deficiency	Present	169	61.23
	Absent	107	38.76
Iodine deficiency	Present	193	69.92
	Absent	83	30.07
Ocular manifestations	conjunctival xerosis	0	0
	Bitot's spots	1	0.36
	corneal xerosis	3	1.08
	keratomalacia	0	0

Discussion:

The prevalence of clinical vitamin A deficiency measured by both Bitot's spots in the present study was determined 0.36%. Vitamin A deficiency (VAD) in rural children is a serious dietary concern with public health implications. Although VAD remains epidemiologically relevant in regions with shared risk factors such as poverty, infectious diseases, and a lack of dietary sources of vitamin A [27], there is evidence that the occurrence of this deficiency has gradually

decreased in recent decades, particularly in low-to-middle income countries [28].

In regard to factors related to the child, there was an association between VAD and stunting. Stunting (growth retardation) is an important indicator of malnutrition because it reflects the long-term cumulative effects of a poor diet and/or recurrent infections[29] and is also associated with low socioeconomic conditions[30,31].

The health system might be bolstered by ensuring that children get enough vitamin A

and develop properly. Thus, given the present nutritional transition situation, it is critical to constantly evaluate public policy, notably universal vitamin A supplementation programs in the towns investigated. Future challenges include investigating dietary behaviors to better understand the findings in order to provide suitable food and nutrition plans for children.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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References

1. Ahmed F. Vitamin A deficiency in Bangladesh: A review and recommendations for improvement. *Public Health Nutr.* 1999;2(1):1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980099000014>.
2. Rahman A, Sapkota M. Knowledge on vitamin a rich foods among mothers of preschool children in Nepal: impacts on public health and policy concerns. *Sci J Public Heal.* 2014;2(4):316–22. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.sjph.20140204.22>.
3. Semba RD, de Pee S, Sun K, Akhter N, Bloem MW, Raju VK. Coverage of vitamin a capsule programme in Bangladesh and risk factors associated with non-receipt of vitamin a. *J Health Popul Nutr.* 2010;28:143
4. Arlappa N, Balakrishna LA, Harikumar N, Brahman R. Clinical and sub-clinical vitamin A deficiency among rural pre-school children of Maharashtra, India. *Ann Hum Biol.* 2010;37(2):282. doi:10.3109/03014460902991979
5. Tsegaye D.T, Ali A, Mekonen Y, Haider J, Umeta M. Magnitude and distribution of vitamin A deficiency in Ethiopia. *Food Nutr Bull.* 2010;31(2):234–241. doi:10.1177/156482651003100206
6. Bates CJ. Vitamin A. *The Lancet.* 1995;345(8941):31–35.
7. Beaton GH. Effectiveness of vitamin A supplementation in the control of young child morbidity and mortality in developing countries. *United Nations Subcommittee on Nutrition (SCN) News.* 1993;9:17–23.
8. UNICEF. Vitamin A Supplementation: a statistical snapshot. Retrieved from <https://data.unicef.org/resources/vitamin-supplementation-statistical-snapshot/>; 2016. Accessed November 30, 2020.
9. Black, R. E. , Allen, L. H. , Bhutta, Z. A. , Caulfield, L. E. , de Onis, M. , Ezzati, M. , ... Rivera, J. (2008). Maternal and child undernutrition: Global and regional exposures and health consequences. *Lancet*, 371, 243–260. 10.1016/S0140-6736(07)61690-0
10. Sachdev, H. , Gera, T. , & Nestel, P. (2005). Effect of iron supplementation on mental and motor development in children: Systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Public Health Nutrition*, 8, 117–132. 10.1079/PHN2004677
11. Igel, L. I. , Saunders, K. H. , & Fins, J. J. (2018). Why weight? An analytic review of obesity management, diabetes prevention, and cardiovascular risk reduction. *Current Atherosclerosis Reports*, 20, 39 10.1007/s11883-018-0740-z
12. Steele, C. B. , Thomas, C. C. , Henley, S. J. , Massetti, G. M. , Galuska, D. A. , Agurs-Collins, T. , ... Richardson, L. C. (2017). Vital signs: Trends in incidence of cancers associated with overweight and

- obesity—United States, 2005-2014. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 66, 1052–1058. 10.15585/mmwr.mm6639e1
13. World Health Organization (2018a). The double burden of malnutrition. http://www.who.int/nutrition/double-burden-malnutrition/infographic_print.pdf?ua=1.
 14. Collins, K. H. , Herzog, W. , MacDonald, G. Z. , Reimer, R. A. , Rios, J. L. , Smith, I. C. , ... Hart, D. A. (2018). Obesity, metabolic syndrome, and musculoskeletal disease: Common inflammatory pathways suggest a central role for loss of muscle integrity. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 9, 112 10.3389/fphys.2018.00112
 15. Ministry of Health Republic of Tajikistan & United Nations Children's Fund (2010) Micronutrient status survey in Tajikistan, 2009. https://www.unicef.org/tajikistan/resources_18750.html (last accessed 6.6.2018).
 16. United Nations Children's Fund (2003) Micronutrient status survey in Tajikistan, 2003. *UNICEF Dushanbe*.
 17. Crivelli, M. , Wyss, K. , Grize, L. , Matthys, B. , Aebi, T. , & Zemp, E. (2018). Are overweight and obesity in children risk factors for anemia in early childhood? Results from a national nutrition survey in Tajikistan. *International Journal of Public Health*, 63, 491–499. 10.1007/s00038-018-1088-4
 18. West, K.P.; Sommer, A.; Palmer, A.; Schultink, W.; Habicht, J.P. Commentary: Vitamin A policies need rethinking. *Int. J. Epidemiol.* 2015, 44, 292–294. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
 19. Bhutta, Z.A.; Baker, S.K. Premature abandonment of global vitamin A supplementation programmes is not prudent! *Int. J. Epidemiol.* 2015, 44, 297–299. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
 20. Benn, C.S.; Fisker, A.B.; Aaby, P. Response to: J Mason et al. Vitamin A policies need 447 rethinking. *Int. J. Epidemiol.* 2015, 44, 366–367. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
 21. Global Alliance for Vitamin A (GAVA). Technical Consultation on Guidance to Vitamin A Supplementation Programs for Children 6–59 Months of Age; GAVA: Ottawa, ON, Canada, 2012. [Google Scholar]
 22. Cappellini, M. D., & Motta, I. (2015). Anemia in clinical practice—denition and classication: does hemoglobin change with aging? Paper presented at the Seminars in hematology. 52(4):261-9. doi:10.1053/j.seminhematol.2015.07.006.
 23. Milman, N. (2011). Anemia—still a major health problem in many parts of the world! *Annals of hematology*, 90(4), 369-377.
 24. Beutler, E., & Waalen, J. (2006). The denition of anemia: what is the lower limit of normal of the blood hemoglobin concentration? *Blood*, 107(5), 1747-1750. doi: 10.1182/blood-2005-07-3046.
 25. World Health Organization. (2011). Haemoglobin concentrations for the diagnosis of anaemia and assessment of severity. Retrieved from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/85839/WHO_NMNH_NHD_MNM_11.1_eng.pdf.
 26. World Health Organization. (2015). The global prevalence of anaemia in 2011. In *The global prevalence of anaemia in 2011*. Retrieved from: https://www.who.int/nutrition/publications/micronutrients/global_prevalence_anemia_2011/en/
 27. Sherwin, JC, Reacher, MH, Dean, WH et al. (2012) Epidemiology of vitamin A deficiency and xerophthalmia in at-risk populations. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg* 106, 205–214.
 28. Stevens, GA, Bennett, JE, Hennocq, Q et al. (2015) Trends and mortality effects of vitamin A deficiency in children in 138 low-income and middle-income countries between 1991 and 2013: a pooled analysis

- of population-based surveys. *Lancet Glob Health* 3, e528–e536.
29. Onis, M, Onyango, AW, Borghi, E et al. (2007) Development of a WHO growth reference for school-aged children and adolescents. *Bull World Health Organ* 85, 660–667.
 30. Haile, D, Azage, M, Mola, T et al. (2016) Exploring spatial variations and factors associated with childhood stunting in Ethiopia: spatial and multilevel analysis. *BMC Pediatr* 16, 49.
 31. Yang, YY, Kaddu, G, Ngendahimana, D et al. (2018) Trends and determinants of stunting among under-5s: evidence from the 1995, 2001, 2006 and 2011 Uganda demographic and health surveys. *Public Health Nutr* 21, 2915–2928.